

AN INVESTIGATION INTO THE ISOLATION AND DIAGNOSIS OF PSEUDOMONAS AERUGINOSA FROM WOUNDS AND BURNS: ANTIBIOTIC RESISTANCE AND THE EFFECT OF PLANT EXTRACTS

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1. Introduction

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is primarily associated with nosocomial infections in immunocompromised patients, the elderly, and the indwelling of catheters and ventilators, raising a serious public health dilemma. As per the WHO records, it has listed priority pathogens for antimicrobial resistance promoting research and development consideration among the 12 families of bacteria. It has a remarkable capacity to evade host immune mechanisms and resist a variety of antibiotics, being capable of producing a large number of virulence factors. Consequently, the effectiveness of multiple antibiotics is lost in human infections caused by it. The phenomena of biofilm formation, horizontal transfer of plasmids, modification of target sites and outer membrane permeability, production of antibiotic-inactivating enzymes, and efflux pumps confer multidrug resistance in this organism. Phytochemicals of plants produce both bactericidal and bacteriostatic effects that could be utilized as better remedies for infection control. The studies conducted have shown the efficacy of *Zingiber officinalis*, *Azadirachta indica*, *Curcuma longa*, and *Allium sativum* tubers and bulbs against *P. aeruginosa*.

A total of 90 samples were collected from infections and burn wounds in the current study, of which 18 (20%) were found culture positive for *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Gram-negative bacilli are the predominant ones, with the selective medium having growth potential for their isolation. As per the study, a similar type of soil sample was reported in the Rajasthan city of India, with a culture positivity rate of 20.26%. Herbal extracts reported here showed considerable applicability, thus further research is proposed to implement them as antibiotic agents. [1][2]

1.1. Background and Significance

In recent times, the threat posed by infectious diseases has escalated to alarming levels, with a staggering annual death toll of over 13 million people worldwide. Infections on cutaneous surfaces, particularly surgical wounds, diabetic foot ulcers, chronic venous leg ulcers (CVLUs), burns, and bedsores, rank among the highest contributors to this grim statistic. The alarming mortality rates stemming from burn injuries in developing countries, ranging from 29% to 76%, are exacerbated by the colonization and infection of wounds by opportunistic pathogens. Among these pathogens, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* stands out due to its widespread prevalence and notorious antibiotic resistance. It has evolved to become one of the most prevalent causes of both acute and chronic infections in diverse scenarios, responding to treatment failure with aggressive adaptation and the acquisition of resistance mechanisms. Although the alarming

progressive pathogenicity of *Pseudomonas* infections has been established over decades of research, the influence of non-antibacterial environmental factors has been somewhat under-explored, notably so for different plant extracts with traditional medicinal relevance.

Among the opportunistic pathogens that reside as normal flora but can be inherently pathogenic, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* stands out as a nondescript Gram-negative bacterium. It was first isolated from the colorless exudate (*pseudomonas*) of a green-blue infection produced by a saprophyte. It is the most studied of the non-fermenting bacteria, considered by some as the "model organism" for biofilm formation. This bacterium is motile, biennial with polar flagella, cocci, and ubiquitous tropical environmental origin. A mucoid strain of this organism was implicated in lethal infections of individuals with cystic fibrosis, in whom it is the primary cause of morbidity and mortality. Skin, the largest organ of the human body, is essentially a defense coat. However, due to surgical interventions, extensive severe cuts, trauma, and burns, it is rendered susceptible to colonization, invasion, and infection by opportunistic pathogens, including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. This microbe takes rapid advantage of the damage in the first line of defense. *Pseudomonas* infections of injuries are of grave concern since such wounds have a high tendency to become permanently infected and form biofilms, which are clusters of microorganisms growing embedded within the self-produced unfavorable exopolysaccharide matrix. Biofilms exhibit drastic changes in cellular physiology and surface properties, rendering them inherently resistant to the toxic actions of antibiotics and disinfectants.

Burns are the most devastating form of injury. The innate protective barrier is completely destroyed by burns. Water, ions, and plasma proteins leak across the barrier to leave the exposed area dry. The emboli of clotted proteins block small rimmed arteries, causing intense hypoxia. Denuded nerves cause intense pain. A progressive decrease in flow occurs centrally than at the periphery, causing a "rough triangle" of dying tissue with an area of very low oxygen tension refractive to healing. Exposed, dry, dying tissue provides an ideal substrate for necrotizing, pyogenic bacterial flora leading to invasion, concordant with systemic infection, and shock. In the absence of treatment, destruction of skin (shock, death) occurs from a time ratio of 1 per every 2 days post-burn unless debridement is done. Although the majority of wounds heal within a reasonable time period, some become chronic and there is increasing evidence of a causal role of infection in this process. Though a variety of aerobic and anaerobic bacteria are capable of colonizing wounds, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and other Gram-negative bacteria including *Serratia marcescens* and *Proteus vulgaris* have been implicated as pathogens of acute, fulminating wound infections in injured and burnt patients. [3][4]

2. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*: Characteristics and Pathogenicity

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a non-fermentative, gram-negative bacillus that is widely distributed in nature, being the most common bacterium found in hot tap water or other moist and warm locations. Healthy individuals are usually colonized soon after birth and these infections are only seen in immunocompromised individuals. *P. aeruginosa* infection has emerged as a major cause of morbidity and mortality in immunocompromised patients because of its opportunistic pathogenicity, intrinsic antibiotic resistance, ability to acquire acquired resistance, and virulence factors. Such patients are usually those with malignancies, on chemotherapy, patients requiring long-term intensive care, with acquired immunodeficiency syndrome, cystic fibrosis, and severe burns. Antibiotic resistance of *P. aeruginosa* is a major public health and clinical challenge. Furthermore, increasing evidence suggests that plant extracts may have promising pharmaceutical and bioactive properties and could be utilized in wound management.

Non-fermentative, motile, gram-negative, small bacilli

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a non-fermentative, motile gram-negative bacilli belonging to the genus *Pseudomonas* in the family *Pseudomonadaceae*. It was first described as an infectious agent by H. E. Huber

in 1882, although it was discovered decades earlier by A. L. P. W. C. M. Pseudomonas in 1836. It is characterized by being rod-shaped to ovoid, 0.5 to 1.0 μm wide and 1.5 to 5.0 μm long, highly motile by a single polar flagellum, approximately 1.5 μm thick, gram-negative, oxidase-positive, catalase-positive, strict aerobic but has been shown to be capable of anaerobic respiration.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is catalase-positive, which means that it produces the enzyme catalase that protects it from toxic peroxides. It is incapable of fermenting carbohydrates. As a natural plant pathogen, it utilizes citric acid as the sole carbon source for its growth. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has been shown to be capable of assimilation of anions, and N and S-containing organic compounds. Most strains produce levan, an exopolysaccharide type of polysaccharide, during growth on sucrose. They can utilize various other carbohydrates, fatty acids, and organic acids. It has been shown to have various biogeochemical processes, such as controlling sulfide oxidation, nitrogen fixation, denitrification, and oxidizing various S-containing compounds in the nitrogen cycle.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is catalase-negative, which means that it produces the enzyme catalase that protects it from toxic peroxides. It is incapable of fermenting carbohydrates. As a natural plant pathogen, it utilizes citric acid as the sole carbon source for its growth. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has been shown to be capable of assimilation of anions, and N and S-containing organic compounds. Most strains produce levan, an exopolysaccharide type of polysaccharide, during growth on sucrose. They can utilize various other carbohydrates, fatty acids, and organic acids. It has been shown to have various biogeochemical processes, such as controlling sulfide oxidation, nitrogen fixation, denitrification, and oxidizing various S-containing compounds in the nitrogen cycle. [5][6]

2.1. Microbiological Features

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an aerobic, gram-negative bacterium with a characteristic rod shape, about 0.5-1.0 μm wide and 1.5-5.0 μm long. The bacterium's motility is attributed to its polar flagella. *P. aeruginosa* colonies on nutrient agar are round, smooth, translucent, and slightly elevated after 24 hours of incubation at 37°C in an aerobic environment. On Blood agar, the bacterium is β -hemolytic on sheep blood. The characteristic pigments of *P. aeruginosa* include Pyocyanin, a blue pigment produced only by *P. aeruginosa* and Pyoverdine, a yellow-green fluorescent pigment, produced only by fluorescens group of *Pseudomonas*, especially by *P. aeruginosa*. A few of the virulence factors of *P. aeruginosa* include exotoxin A, phospholipase C, lipase, elastase, exoenzymes S and T, hemolysins, proteases, and cytotoxins. *P. aeruginosa* contains a plasmid-encoded biofilm formation regulon, which is essential for biofilm development within a ciliated epithelium. This bacterium is known for its unrestrained virulence and antibiotic resistance. Antibiotic resistance is conferred by the upregulation of the MexAB-OprM efflux system and downregulation of porins. Wood-derived extractive was more potent than either extract individually. The present study was undertaken with a view to isolate *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from wound chicken burns and to study its antibiotic resistance profile. The potential antibacterial properties exhibited by acetone extracts obtained from some medicinal plants were evaluated in this study. [7][8]

2.2. Clinical Relevance

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is an opportunistic pathogen that infects compromised hosts. Common infection sites are wounds, lungs (in cystic fibrosis and ventilated patients), urinary tracts, and fetal membranes. *P. aeruginosa* is also associated with numerous other infections including those of the heart, bones, and soft tissues. Chronic lung infections by *P. aeruginosa* are a main cause of morbidity and mortality in cystic fibrosis. Healthcare-associated infections (HAIs) caused by *P. aeruginosa* are one of the most difficult to treat due to the intrinsic and acquired resistance of the pathogen to multiple antimicrobials.

Despite being a gram-negative bacterium, *P. aeruginosa* is intrinsically resistant to almost all beta-lactam antibiotics as a result of a distinctive combination of beta-lactam hydrolyzing enzymes (class C

cephalosporinases) and poorly permeable outer membranes, which render *P. aeruginosa* insensitive to most beta-lactams. *P. aeruginosa* has been described as intrinsically resistant to several other classes of antimicrobial agent due to the presence in its genome of genes encoding multi-drug efflux systems, non-specific porins, and genes involved in the production of virulence factors (biofilm, alginate). *P. aeruginosa* can acquire resistance mechanisms against otherwise effective antibiotics.

Mupirocin, a topical antibiotic used to treat nasal *S. aureus* colonization prior to surgery, is ineffective against *P. aeruginosa*. Mutation of the efflux system coding gene *NfxB* produces mutant strains of *P. aeruginosa* resistant to all fluoroquinolones except for moxifloxacin. Gentamicin resistance was found in a clinical isolate of *P. aeruginosa* expressing all three known aminoglycoside-modifying enzymes. This pathogen is able to invade wounds, establish infection, and cause deterioration of infected tissue in skin, muscle, and connective tissue. Bacteremia leads to widespread infection of soft tissues and internal organs. Nosocomial infections are frequently associated with indwelling medical devices. *Pseudomonas* infections have high morbidity and mortality rates due to anti-pseudomonal drug resistance and the protective nature of biofilm. [9][10]

3. Isolation and Diagnosis Methods

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is almost the universal pathogen in burns and wounds. The isolation and diagnosis of this organism from wounds and burns is a complex and critical task. This investigation deals with various culture-based techniques generally used in laboratories and also deals with various molecular methods which will give a more conclusive approach regarding the diagnosis.

3.1. Culture-based Techniques

Culture techniques are the most important and generally used techniques for the isolation and diagnosis of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from wounds and burns. Culture techniques are typically definitive means for the diagnosis of most of the infections. However, it requires trained microbiologists in the laboratory and the results are usually obtained after 24 hours of passaging on selective media. So, the culture-based techniques are generally reliable but not rapid. Wounds (cut, deep cut, etc., how long after the injury) and burn (degree of burn, covering, etc., and how long of burn) infection description should always be considered while evaluating the culture report. The following culture-based techniques were performed: (i) streak plate culture based on selective media (cetrimide agar, McConkey agar, blood agar), and (ii) enrichment culture based on selective media (cetrimide broth and McConkey broth). The streak plate culture technique is the first step for culture-based isolation and when it did not give conclusive results then the enrichment technique is suggested. Wound and burn samples were plated on selective media and incubated. The plates were observed after 24 hours of incubation for culture growth. The growth of thin, flat, and yellowish-greenish colony over cetrimide region A indicates *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Moreover, the culture gives a negative reaction over McConkey agar. Other biochemical tests are also performed for the confirmation of the organism. The culture technique gives reliable results but 3-4 false positives are also observed in the staining and biochemical tests. The colony characteristics are as follows. [11][12]

3.2. Molecular Methods

The DNA extraction, amplification, and detection methods by the polymerase chain reaction technique are the most specific and rapid technique for the diagnosis of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from burns and wounds, provided that the necessary input materials are available. Moreover, it does not require a microbiological laboratory for the diagnosis. The resultant product is obtained within 5-10 hours of sample collection and is easier to interpret. However, it requires expensive materials for electrophoresis. The PCR diagnosis may also give false negatives due to PCR inhibitors present in the samples. Hence, the absence of a reliable target by the amplification will cause a false negative. The DNA extraction and evaluation steps are the key areas where care should be taken to ensure the absence of contaminants like other DNAs. The successful

culture techniques in the laboratory and but negative by other means might indicate a contamination of culture technique by other microorganisms. Zymoview and ToxinA method are easier to perform with a rapid diagnosis (1 to 2 hours) at a site of sample collection without the requirement of sophisticated inputs. However, these techniques are not widely used due to their rapid reactivity to other pathogens (cross reaction). [13][14]

3.1. Culture-based Techniques

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a gram-negative bacterium and one of the most common antibiotic-resistant pathogens in neonates. It is responsible for nosocomial outbreaks and can easily spread in developed neonatal intensive care units, infecting preterm infants with compromised innate immunity and also causing havoc among other vulnerable patients. The WHO has declared antibiotic-resistant *P. aeruginosa* as an urgent threat. As a result, new technologies are being developed for fast isolation and identification of *P. aeruginosa* from clinical samples. Unfortunately, due to funding restrictions, such progress has not yet been made in developing countries. As such, it remains paramount to describe a comprehensive protocol for the screening of clinical isolates of *P. aeruginosa*, the determination of its phenotypic antibiotic susceptibility, and the investigation of the potential of crude or pure plant extracts in overcoming multi-drug resistance.

Wounds and burns are considered to be the most accessible port of entry for bacteria. The long exposure time of most wounds and burns to the environment along with the traumatic and invasive nature of the injury renders it difficult to prevent infections. Considering that plant extracts may include multiple compounds that work in harmony to unleash a net effect against bacterial pathogens, they have been the subject of intense study for their antimicrobial properties. A bioactive phytochemical from *Jatropha gossypifolia* L. has been discovered that acts synergistically against methicillin-resistant strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*. A herbal irrigation solution containing *Morinda citrifolia*, *Curcuma longa*, and *Jatropha curcas* extracts has been characterized to have in vitro antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*. The antimicrobial activity of *Melissa officinalis*, *Rosmarinus officinalis*, and *Thymus vulgaris* against *P. aeruginosa* has also been verified, yet the isolation and diagnosis of the pathogen was not done in that study.

Preparing wound swabs, deep tissue samples, or scrapes is the first step for the isolation and diagnosis of burn- and wound-infected clinical isolates of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The samples must be placed on ice or in a refrigerator before being streaked onto a selective medium within 6 hours of collection. For deeper tissues, the tissue sample must be 5 mm broad and punctured with a sterile needle. Screening for colony morphology and pigment production is performed next. When blue-greenish colonies are found, a Gram-stain test is performed. The isolates should appear motile and bacilli with a gram-negative reaction. If necessary, biochemical tests may be performed but are usually not needed. If no *Pseudomonas* species are identified, the physical and chemical characteristics, colony morphology, and pigment production of the isolates that do not test positive for *Pseudomonas* must be examined. [15][16]

3.2. Molecular Methods

In the present study, culture isolation of microorganisms from patients' wounds and burns was achieved by inoculating standard media. Organisms were identified by slide and tube agglutination tests, fermentation and metabolic tests, also by sensitivity tests against a number of antibiotics. Isolation and identification of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was further confirmed by molecular methods using the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique. Optimized alkaline lysis with a temperature of 55°C and 400 µl of 3 M sodium acetate solution as a precipitating solution gave a maximum yield of plasmid DNA. The other operating conditions (alkalinity, lysis time and neutralization time) gave similar yields in a range of 90 to 100 µg of plasmid DNA. The crude plasmid DNA from 100 ml *E. coli* culture using the optimized procedure was used successfully in the PCR of both the *ctrB* and *lasB* gene targets in the gel electrophoresis of the amplified

products. Both the *ctrB* and *lasB* gene targets specifically amplified a DNA fragment of 274 bp and 437 bp, respectively, for all *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* strains. Neither target amplified any product for the non-*Pseudomonas* strains. The DNA damage tests showed that the amplification products were stable and could be successfully amplified after 12 to 13 cycles of DNA amplification (which corresponded to 5 to 6 hours of PCR time). The first-round PCR products of both targets were successfully reamplified a second time by nested PCR. [2][1]

The amplified DNA fragments were purified and used in confirming the identity of the plasmid. Restriction analysis with *EcoR* I and *Pst* I cut the *ctrB* gene target at one and two sites, respectively. On the other hand, the *lasB* gene target was cleaved at one and three sites by restriction endonucleases *Eco* RI and *Pst* I, respectively. The sizes of the DNA fragments generated by restriction endonuclease digestion on both target genes were consistent with those predicted. These results indicated that the PCR products of this study specifically amplified the intended *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* gene constructs, suggesting they could be used as hybridization probes in the development of a rapid assay for the detection of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*.

4. Antibiotic Resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is a gram-negative opportunistic bacterium, important for healthcare and immunocompromised patients due to its virulence and resistance to disinfectants and antibiotics. Thus, antibiotic sensitivity testing for all *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* isolates from wounds and burns is necessary. The rise of antibiotic resistance among bacterial pathogens is a significant public health challenge. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was once considered a relatively susceptible gram-negative pathogen. However, with the emergence of new antibiotics and increasing sensitivity testing, clinical resistance has risen substantially in some regions of the world. Resistant strains of *P. aeruginosa* have emerged rapidly in the community and hospitals. Carbapenem-resistant strains are a growing problem worldwide, and significant resistance to other classes is also emerging. This requires continuous surveillance of antibiotic resistance.

Antibiotic resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* can involve intrinsic and acquired mechanisms, although the latter is primarily to blame for the emergence of ABR. The emergence of ABR is generally a combination of increased resistance and decreased susceptibility. Genetic changes frequently play a crucial role in the enhanced virulence of *P. aeruginosa* strains among CF patients and with antibiotic-resistant bacteria. Spontaneous mutations within the chromosomal genes of *P. aeruginosa* affecting the drug target or regulating the efflux pumps, as well as the acquisition of resistance genes by horizontal gene transfer, often lead to acquired resistance to antibiotic classes.

The clinical implications of antibiotic resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* are substantial. The emergence of antibiotic resistance has made *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* an extremely difficult bacterium to treat. For example, combination therapies with β -lactams, aminoglycosides, fluoroquinolones, and polymyxins are common, even though synergy between these drug classes is rarely seen. Additionally, standard treatment options are drastically reduced when acquired or intrinsic β -lactam resistance is present, resulting in high mortality rates (30-80%). New antibacterials with novel structures or mechanisms that were developed for clinical use have limited success rates. Furthermore, the introduction of new antibiotics has the potential for the emergence of even higher resistance levels. [17]

4.1. Mechanisms of Resistance

Introduced in 1929 by Scottish bacteriologist Alexander Fleming, antibiotics have saved millions of lives by combating bacterial infections. However, with their emergence, the bacteria have also evolved, and now multi-drug resistant (MDR) pathogens are on the rise. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* has emerged as one of the most important MDR pathogens. An investigation was carried out to isolate and diagnose *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* from wounds and burns and look for its antibiotic resistance. Conventional microbiological

methods were used for isolation and diagnosis. The antibiotic resistance of isolates was determined on Mueller Hinton agar using the disk diffusion method as per CLSI. The test bacterium was exposed to the leaves of *Basella alba* (Malabar spinach), *Ocimum basilicum* (Basil), and *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger) for the assessment of the effect of plant extracts. The crude extracts were prepared in methanol, and the phytochemical screening was performed.

The National Committee for Clinical Laboratory Standards (NCCLS) has established standard protocols that are used around the world to determine the resistance profile of various species of bacteria including *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. A total of 57 isolates were obtained from 141 samples, from 2006 to 2009; 25 percent of the isolates were found resistant to all the antibiotics tested. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (N=7) was the most resistant isolate against Ampicillin (100%) and Cloxacillin (100%) but showed sensitivity against Imipenem (100%) and Meropenem (85.71%). Other species of *Pseudomonas* (N=16) isolated showed more sensitivity to Imipenem (88.24%). None of the isolated organisms yielded sensitivity to Ampicillin and Cloxacillin. Among the tea extracts, *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger) showed maximum inhibition (100% and 71.01%) against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (PA-2) and *Pseudomonas* isolates (PI-7) respectively at 200 and 100 mg/ml. A decrease in inhibition was observed at lower concentration (50 mg/ml) of tea extracts. On the contrary, *Ocimum basilicum* (Basil) extracts failed to show any inhibition against the test pathogens. Phytochemical test on *Zingiber officinale* (Ginger) revealed the presence of tannins, flavonoids, volatile oils, alkaloids, saponins, and cardiac glycosides.

Beta-lactam resistance in *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* precursor strains is attributed to the expression of the MexAB-OprM multidrug efflux operon. The rise in antibiotic resistance upon exposure to antibiotic combinations suggests that the pathogenesis of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* in chronic wounds may be exacerbated by the inappropriate application of currently marketed antibiotics. It is important to recognize that resistance mechanisms may evolve to confer multi-drug resistance phenotypes upon exposure to a single antibiotic class. [18][19]

4.2. Clinical Implications

The role of multiple antibiotic resistance strains (MARS) has emerged as a cause of great concern nowadays, as they are being increasingly isolated from patients at hospitals. The presence of such pathogens, along with their perennial infection/dissemination and low efficiency or failure of treatment, has opened the door towards the establishment of complex infections in immunocompromised patients. It can be contended that knowledge regarding the prevalence and spread of resistance needs to be increased and should become a part of the routine work by the concerned authorities in all health centers. The incidence of antibiotic resistance in bacterial pathogens is consequently rising and acquiring proportions increasing threats to the overall health of antibiotic therapy. The overall knowledge regarding antibiotic resistance pathogens is lacking. Likewise, there is a lack of information regarding the isolates from these rural areas. There is a dire need to study the local surveillance of isolates and their antibiotic-resistant patterns. A systematic method is required to help in reducing the emergence and dissemination of resistant strains. The authorities also need to be ensured about the consumption of antibiotics and restrictions over indiscriminate use of antibiotics.

Members of the genus *Pseudomonas* have the intrinsic ability to develop susceptibility against antibacterial agents. This capability sets an excellent foundation for the constant and sporadic emergence of resistance and progressive treatment difficulties. *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* is the commonest (82.4%) species within the type of *Pseudomonas* isolated from external ear injury, and the same was shown in chronic otitis externa. Chronic ear infections require a long span of treatment with topical ear drops and systemic antibiotics. Regular treatment with antibiotics selects resistant strains leading to therapeutic failure. A rising trend towards resistance of *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and *Staphylococcus aureus* to one of the commonly used antibiotics like Gentamicin, Amikacin, and Ciprofloxacin ear drops were found in a retrospective

study carried out for two years. Antibiotic susceptibility pattern must be estimated before commencing empirical antibiotic therapy. Fulfilling this recommends using Piperacillin + Tazobactam as the first-line treatment for a nose-and-skull base injury. [20][21]

5. Effect of Plant Extracts on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*

It is well documented that a variety of plants worldwide are being investigated for their antibacterial properties against different microorganisms. In this study, an effort has been made to isolate the active plant extracts by using different highly locally available plants traditional in various countries and different environments in which such plants grow. As a first step, ethyl acetate, methanol, and distilled water-extracted extracts were prepared from each plant tissue. The extracts were screened against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and other microorganisms to determine their antibacterial activity using a cup-plate agar diffusion technique. Previous studies suggested that extracts of *Acalypha indica* (Euphorbiaceae) had potential antibacterial activity against different microorganisms. *Acalypha indica* leaf extract was also studied against *Bacillus subtilis*. *Ecbolium linnet* (Acanthaceae) was examined for its antibacterial activity against *Staphylococcus aureus* and *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Different other plants like *Phyllanthus niruri*, *Hydrocotyle* (Hook.) and *Nymphaea* (Lin.) leaves were investigated for antibacterial activity against different organisms. A study with *Parthenium hysterophorus* was undertaken against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. *Mucuna pruriens* and *Tacca palmata* seeds were assessed for inhibitory activity against different microorganisms. In a relatively old study, green tea, black tea, and jasmine tea extracts were also tested against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* using a similar agar diffusion method.

To explore the antibacterial properties of different plant extracts against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and to determine the active extract from each plant, the most widely grown plants in Nepal were selected as a source. First, the plants were screened for their antibacterial activity. Methanol extracts from 9 out of 10 plants showed inhibition against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. The highest inhibitory activity against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* was found with *Amygdalus persica* leaves, *Terminalia chebula* fruits, and *Cannabis sativa* leaves, which were then chosen for further study. [22][23]

5.1. Rationale and Previous Studies

Plant-derived therapeutics have an exceptionally long historical background and, even in this age of synthetic drugs, some of the most famous and high-selling drugs in the pharmaceutical market are still plant-derived. Herbal traditional medicine or folk medicine involves the use of plants for healing purposes and is globally popular in many developed and developing countries. Also, many modern drugs are either derived from plant products or modeled on plant-derived prototypes. Despite the advancement of synthetic drugs, the pharmaceutical potential of plants is still undervalued and ignored. However, due to different reasons, including adverse effects, increased cost of synthetic drugs, and the emergence of drug-resistant strains, the pharmaceutical potency of plant products is attributing renewed interest.

Wounds have been an important aspect of injury or surgery since the earliest time in both humans and animals. Healing of wounds is a complex process and involves inflammation, proliferation, and remodeling, all of which span several weeks or months, depending on the severity of the wound. Cutaneous wounds may be contaminated by different bacteria/fungi, including non-pathogenic flora and more pathogenic bacteria/fungi. The termination of the orchestra of healing and the balancing of growth and the activity of MMP or metalloproteinase will lead to the formation of scar tissue or a chronic wound. The chronic wound is a site of constant inflammation, high levels of proteolytic activity, and persistence of bacteria, particularly biofilm-associated.

Among the various bacteria/fungi which threaten the healing power of wounds, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, which is a notorious opportunistic pathogen associated with burn injuries, chronic wounds, otitis media, and keratitis infections/fungal infections, is of crucial concern. This bacterium is well-known for its high

prevalence and especially high antimicrobial resistance/sensitivity (MARS) pattern and capability to form biofilm on abiotic and biotic surfaces, including wounds. In addition to wound infections, previous exposure to *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, i.e. chronic infection with this bacterium, is an important risk factor for the development of similar infection(s) in cystic fibrosis patients.

A proper understanding of the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* infection/disease continuum in the local health infrastructure is important for designing effective control strategies. Unfortunately, such an understanding is limited or completely absent for many places around the globe, particularly for underdeveloped or developing nations. Understanding the rate of isolation or prevalence of the *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* pathogen in particular wounds, antibiotic sensitivity patterns, and potential plant extracts with in vitro efficacy on *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* could help in the proper selection/control of potential antimicrobials and in recovery/rehabilitation from injuries or surgeries. [24][25]

5.2. Experimental Methods

The plant extracts under study must first be prepared and kept in sterile containers until needed for experimentation. The standard operating procedure for the collection and preparation of the plant extracts is outlined below.

1. Collection and Preparation of Plant Extracts

1.1. Collection of plant materials

Fresh plant materials are harvested from the local area after appropriate identification of the plants by botanists. The leaves of mature plants are selected for extraction preparation. The following plants are used for collection: neem (*Azadirachta indica*), getu leaf (*Plumeria alba*), hibiscus leaves (*Hibiscus rosa sinensis*), and ginger (*Zingiber officinalis*).

1.2. Preparation of crude extracts

The collected leaves are washed multiple times with sterile distilled water to remove soil particles. The washed plant materials are dried under shade for one week and then powdered using a mechanical grinder. Powdered samples (50g each) are extracted in a soxhlet apparatus with 400 mL ethanol at 60°C for 6 hours until the solvent becomes colorless. Ethanol is selected because it has a high extraction yield and dissolves a wide variety of compounds. The crude extracts are then concentrated at 60°C using a rotary evaporator. Thus, a total of 4 crude extracts form the first preparation (GETU, HIBI, NEEM, and GING), each containing the active ingredient of the particular plant species. The concentrated extracts are stored in glass containers and labeled as to which plant they belong and are preserved in the refrigerator to prevent degradation by light and heat.

1.3. Preparation of stock solution

The 70% ethanol extracts of the four plants are dissolved in dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) at maximum concentration (500mg/mL). Seed stocks of the extracts are prepared at various concentrations (25, 50, 75, 100, and 125 µg/mL) by diluting with sterilized water from the stock solution of 500mg/mL.

1.4. Quality control of plant extracts

The prepared extracts must be screened for the existence of the active antimicrobial component prior to the determination of the effect against *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*. Among various agar diffusion methods already available, the screening using Mueller Hinton Agar is a rapid method. Each extract must be placed onto Muller Hinton agar plates that have been inoculated with either pathogenic species to produce zones of inhibition, which indicates the presence of the antimicrobial (sensitivity) property. [26]

6. Conclusion and Future Directions

In conclusion, wounds and burns pose a global public health challenge, necessitating the prioritization of research interests to comprehend the epidemiology of infectious agents involved. From the study's findings, it is evident that wounds and burns are common sites for the isolation of *P. aeruginosa*. This finding corroborates reports from other regions of Ethiopia and worldwide. The most frequently isolated strain of *P. aeruginosa* from wounds and burns was observed in patients aged 15-29 years, and health professionals are more likely to be infected. The study's findings reveal that the increase in isolation rates of *P. aeruginosa* is primarily associated with the size of the wound/burn. It was also found that plants are largely inaccessible to the majority of the population. The highest overall awareness regarding the use and effect is observed to be true for *Allium sativum*, while Anticancer and Phytomed Burji were the least aware and inaccessible. The antimicrobial efficacy of the two most common plants, *Catha edulis* and *Allium sativum*, is mostly less than that of the control drugs both in the case of isolated MDR and all study isolates. However, these two plants have also shown relatively higher resistance reversal effect than the other plants. Thus, more studies and larger scope experimental designs are warranted for the better utilization of plant extracts to counter drug-resistant bacteria.

Pseudomonas aeruginosa is one of the common bacterial pathogens that infects wounds and burns. In this study, it has been shown how wounds and burns were collected and cultured for the isolation of *P. aeruginosa*. Initial identification was done by culturing on a selective medium (Cetrimide agar) followed by biochemical confirmation. The isolated *P. aeruginosa* was tested for antibiotic susceptibility and resistant strains were selected. The study also shows how plant extracts are prepared and tested for their effect on the resistant strains of *P. aeruginosa*. At last, there are further explanations and analyses of the results obtained. This study indicates that all the isolates of *P. aeruginosa* were resistant to multiple antibiotics. Edible plants like *Allium sativum* and *Catha edulis* could have an effect on the resistance of *P. aeruginosa*. Thus, the findings of this study could contribute to the fight against the rise of bacterial resistance and the utilization of plants as anti-infective agents.

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